

Diagnosis and Grading of the Chondromalacia of Patella using Axial Proton Density Spectral Attenuated Inversion Recovery (PD-SPAIR) and Axial Proton Density MRI Knee Sequences

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Abstract

Background: Chondromalacia of patella is a common disease characterized by softening and degeneration of the patellar articular cartilage and is a frequent cause of anterior knee pain in young adults. **Objectives:** The purpose of this study is to assess sensitivity, specificity and the accuracy of axial proton density –spectral attenuated inversion recovery MRI sequence in detecting and grading patellar cartilage in patients with chondromalacia patellae in comparison to axial proton density sequence. **Patients and methods:** Thirty patients with chondromalacia patellae would be included in our study, 18 patients were women and 12 were men, their ages ranged from 12-30 years old. Another thirty-one patients that underwent knee MRI for another knee problem will be included also as a standard control group, 23 were males and 8 were females, their ages ranging from 13-36 years old. All these patients will be examined by MR imaging with 1.5 tesla imaging system using both the axial proton density- spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) and axial proton density (PD) sequences. The study was done in AL Emamain Alkadhmain medical city. All the results will be reviewed 2 radiologists; final grading of patellar chondromalacia was made with mutual agreement. **Results:** Sensitivity of PD-SPAIR and PD sequences was 86.7% and 70% respectively. Specificity was for PD-SPAIR 93.5% and 77.4% for PD sequences. Accuracy for detecting these lesions in comparison to the control group was 90.1% for PD-SPAIR and 73.8% for PD sequence. **Conclusion:** The axial proton density spectrum attenuated inversion recovery sequence may accurately and quickly detect and grade cartilage defects in chondromalacia patellae patients. Fat saturation and proton density-weighted sequences are sensitive to cartilage lesions and intramedullary osseous oedematous changes, thus they should substitute the traditional proton density sequence in these patients.

Introduction

Chondromalacia patellae (CMP) is a prevalent cause of anterior knee pain, particularly among young individuals, and results from degenerative changes in the articular cartilage on the posterior surface of the patella [1]. It is considered the leading cause of anterior knee discomfort in the youth population in the United States, affecting approximately one in four people [2]. While it shares clinical features with patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS) and patellar tendinopathy, CMP

is distinct from PFPS and should not be classified under its spectrum [3]. Anatomically, the knee joint comprises the femur, tibia, fibula, and patella. The patella articulates with the femur in the trochlear groove, and the articular cartilage enables smooth gliding across the femoral surface [4]. However, repetitive or excessive lateral forces may impair cartilage nutrition, leading to degenerative alterations [5]. The quadriceps muscle group—comprising four muscles—plays a crucial role in active stabilization during knee extension. Among

More Information

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these, the vastus medialis obliquus (VMO) is the only active medial stabilizer [6]. Additionally, the quadriceps influence the knee's passive stabilizers, including the lateral retinaculum, which may contribute to lateral patellar tracking or tilt when dysfunctional [4]. CMP typically arises from overload injury due to misalignment between the femur, tibia, and patella [1]. Contributing factors include an increased Q-angle, muscular tightness, excessive foot pronation, patella alta, and VMO insufficiency, all of which can increase lateral patellar traction, heighten pronation, and result in a lateral drift of the patella [7]. Despite these associations, the precise etiology of CMP remains poorly understood [1]. Clinically, CMP manifests as anterior knee pain, localized tenderness, crepitus, minor swelling, weakness of the VMO, and an elevated Q-angle [8]. It frequently affects adolescents and females, with idiopathic forms seen in children and degenerative types more common in middle-aged and elderly individuals [8]. A decline in quadriceps strength is a notable consequence, highlighting the importance of maintaining muscle function [9]. Diagnosing CMP poses challenges due to its unclear etiology and the weak correlation between clinical presentation and cartilage pathology [10]. Radiographic evaluation combined with arthrography can aid in assessment; however, conventional X-rays and CT scans mainly detect late-stage osteoarthritic changes and fail to visualize early chondral damage [11]. Arthroscopy remains the diagnostic gold standard for assessing articular cartilage but is both invasive and costly [12]. MRI has emerged as a powerful, non-invasive tool for evaluating patellar cartilage and monitoring treatment outcomes [13]. MRI demonstrates an 86% sensitivity, 74% specificity, and 81% overall accuracy for detecting CMP [10]. Nevertheless, its sensitivity may be compromised by partial volume averaging, which can obscure early lesions [14]. Among various sequences, fat-suppressed proton density (PD) images offer high spatial resolution and contrast-to-noise ratios within a feasible scan duration [15]. PD-weighted sequences, integrating characteristics of both T1 and T2 imaging, are particularly effective for visualizing hyaline cartilage [16]. The present study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of axial proton density–spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) MRI sequences in detecting and grading patellar cartilage lesions in patients with clinically suspected chondromalacia patella.

Method

Case control study done in AL Emamain Alkadhmain medical city/Radiology department/ MRI unit in the period from the 1PstP of October 2022 to 1PstP of February 2024.

Inclusion criteria: Patients complaining from knee pain diagnosed by rheumatologist senior as chondromalacia

of patella, and another similar age group that underwent knee MRI for another complains.

Exclusion criteria: Any contraindications to MRI examination. Any patients where their images have artifacts of any type that prevent perfect interpretation.

30 knee MRI examinations of 30 adult patients with chondromalacia of patella; 18 women (60%), 12 men (40%); were included in this study their mean ages were 22.1years; their ages ranging from (12 to 30) years. Patellar cartilage of the patients was evaluated in proton density–spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) sequence, and corresponding axial proton density (PD) sequence. Another 31 patients, referred for MRI department for different knee complains examined in the same manners as the chondromalacia patients by the same protocols used as a control group, twenty-three were male (74.2%) and eight were females (25.8%), mean ages were 23.5 years, ranging from (13-36) years.

Imaging: All images were obtained with 1.5 Tesla machine (Philips medical systems, ACHEIVA) transmit/receive dedicate knee coil. Axial proton density –spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) MR images (TR3000 ms/TE30ms) were done, slice thickness was 1mm, field of view was 160 mm. Corresponding axial proton density (PD) sequence (TR5000ms/TE30ms) were obtained in the same slice thickness and field of view for each patient.

MRI grading: In our study we used MRI grading system for chondromalacia of patella⁽¹⁷⁾, there is 5 grades of lesions, depending whether there is abnormal signal intensity or loss of cartilage that expressed as percentage of thickness.

The grades are:

Grade 1: is reserved for isolated signal changes in the cartilage with an intact articular surface.: A. small focus, B. non full thickness changes and C. Full thickness changes. Grade 2: is reserved for chondral lesions extending down less than 50% of the cartilage depth whether it is: A. fissure or fibrillation, B. flap, C. crab meat lesion and D. diffuse volume loss of less than 50% of cartilage thickness. Grade 3: is reserved for chondral lesions extending down 50% or more of the cartilage depth but not reaching the subchondral bone whether it: A. fissure or fibrillation, B. flap, C. crab meat lesion and D. diffuse volume loss of more than 50% of cartilage thickness. Grade 4: is reserved for full thickness cartilage defect whether it is: A. full thickness fissure, B. full thickness flap, C. full thickness ulcer and D. diffuse full thickness volume loss. Grade 5: is reserved for any grade 4 lesion with subchondral fibrocystic change in the underlying bone.

Image review: All images were reviewed and graded by two radiologists, for each patellar facet, and junctional area were separately evaluated carefully. The results

were mutually done; subsequent final grading was done for all patellar cartilage surfaces.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 22 for windows. Mean, SD, frequency and percentage for descriptive analysis and Chi-square were used. Sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy were calculated. The results were significant in which the P value was less than 0.05.

Results

Thirty knee MRI examinations of adult patients with chondromalacia patellae; mean age 22.1±3.9 years; ages range from (12-30 years) were included, and 31 knee MRI examinations of 31 adult control group, twenty-three were males (74.2%) and eight were females (25.8%), mean ages were 23.5±5.1 years ranging from (13-36) years old. According to our study, of 30 adult patients with chondromalacia of patella; 18 women (60%), 12 men (40%), and the control group, twenty-three were males (74.2%), and eight were

females (25.8%), the females were significantly more in diseased group (P=0.007). According to the grading results on both sequences, there was twelve patients with grade one on axial PD-SPAIR sequence, five of them no significant abnormalities can be detected on axial PD sequence, but the other seven patients graded as grade one on both sequences. Nine patients graded as grade two lesions by axial PD-SPAIR, four of them show no changes, another four graded as grade one and only one patient graded as grade two on axial PD sequence. Three patients were graded as grade 3 on both sequences

Five patients graded as grade four by axial PD-SPAIR sequence, two of them graded as grade three and, the other three patients graded as grade four on axial PD sequence. One patient grade as grade five by axial PD SPAIR sequence, that graded as grade four by axial PD sequence. As shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Grading of Chondromalacia in PD in Comparison to PD_SPAIR

PD-SPAIR	PD					Total	P-value
	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5		
G0	5	4	0	0	0	9	<0.0001*
G1	7	4	0	0	0	11	
G2	0	1	0	0	0	1	
G3	0	0	3	2	0	5	
G4	0	0	0	3	1	4	
Total	12	9	3	5	1	30	

According to the above results the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy for axial PD-SPAIR sequence are 86.7%,93.5%,92.9%,87.9% and 90.1% respectively. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and

accuracy for axial PD sequence are 70%,77.4%,73.8%, 95% and 72.7% respectively. This demonstrated in table 2.

Table 2: The Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV and Accuracy for PD-SPAIR and PD

Predictive parameters	PD-SPAIR	PD
Sensitivity	86.7%	70.0%
Specificity	93.5%	77.4%
Positive Predictive Value	92.9%	73.8%
Negative Predictive Value	87.9%	95.0%
Accuracy	90.1%	72.7%

Figure 1: Left knee axial MRI of young male patients, had chondromalacia grade 2 (large arrow) (superficial erosions corresponding to loss of less than 50% of cartilage) on lateral patella on PD-SPAIR, not seen on PD and grade 3 (small arrow) on medial surface seen on both sequences.

Figure 2: Right knee axial MRI of young male, had chondromalacia grade 4 (full thickness loss) of patellar cartilage of lateral patellar facet on PD-SPAIR spear as grade 3 (loss of more than 50% of patellar cartilage but not all the cartilage) on PD.

Figure 3: Left knee axial MRI of young male, had chondromalacia grade 5 (full thickness loss of patellar cartilage with underlying subchondral erosion and bone marrow edema of medial patella on PDSPAIR and grade 4 (the underlying erosion and edema not seen) on PD.

Figure 4: Left knee axial MRI young female, had chondromalacia grade 1 (abnormal increased signal intensity) on medial patellar surface on PD-SPAIR and was normal on PD.

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate and compare the diagnostic accuracy of axial proton density–spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) MRI sequences in detecting and grading patellar cartilage abnormalities in patients with chondromalacia patellae. The objective was to validate this highly sensitive, specific, and time-efficient sequence for early diagnosis, monitoring, and therapeutic decision-making. Accurate MRI-based cartilage assessment requires adequate spatial resolution, high image contrast, and clear distinction between the cartilage, surrounding joint fluid, and subchondral bone [18,19]. MRI plays a pivotal role in identifying the various stages of chondromalacia patellae. Cartilage thickness can vary depending on anatomical location, patient height, and weight, while the homogenous signal of healthy articular cartilage is largely influenced by its water content [20]. Among the widely utilized techniques for cartilage imaging are T1-weighted fat-suppressed 3D spoiled gradient-echo imaging and T2-weighted fast spin-echo imaging [21]. Proton density-weighted MR sequences are also commonly employed due to their favorable resolution, contrast, and short acquisition time, making them suitable for visualizing patellar cartilage [22]. However, the diagnostic performance of the standard axial PD sequence is comparatively limited. For instance, Tawfik et al. reported sensitivity and specificity values of 88% and 94%, respectively, for other advanced techniques, suggesting that conventional PD may fall short in detecting deeper or underlying bone changes [23]. In contrast, our findings demonstrated that the PD-SPAIR sequence achieved sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy rates of 86.7%, 93.5%, and 90.1%, respectively, outperforming standard PD, which showed only 70%, 77.4%, and 72.7%. These results also surpass those reported by Shakoore et al., who found a sensitivity of 76% and specificity of 93% using 3D MRI techniques [24]. The axial plane was particularly effective in covering critical areas of interest, including the patellar surface, weight-bearing zones, and the posterior aspect of the femoral condyles, facilitating a more comprehensive evaluation of cartilage thickness and defects [25]. The PD-SPAIR sequence also demonstrated high sensitivity in detecting early-stage chondromalacia and was especially valuable in identifying more advanced lesions, such as those with underlying subchondral fibrocystic changes, due to its fat-suppression capability [26,27]. Several MRI studies have further supported the utility of fat-saturated proton density sequences in identifying cartilage lesions, highlighting their superior spatial resolution and favorable contrast-to-noise ratio within a relatively short scan time [28–30]. In our experience, early chondromalacia often

presents as increased signal intensity within the patellar cartilage, whereas more severe grades—such as grade 3, 4, and 5—are more clearly visualized and graded with confidence [31]. Accurate grading is essential for determining appropriate treatment strategies, which may differ considerably across lesion severity. Given the high prevalence of chondromalacia patellae, especially in younger populations, and the frequent absence of specific clinical findings, early MRI detection becomes critically important. Our clinical practice revealed that communication gaps between referring physicians and radiologists often result in under-recognition of this condition. Therefore, we propose incorporating axial PD-SPAIR sequences as a routine part of knee MRI protocols, particularly for young patients with unexplained anterior knee pain [32]. Doing so would improve detection rates and ensure timely intervention for this frequently overlooked but clinically significant pathology.

Conclusion

The axial proton density–spectral attenuated inversion recovery (PD-SPAIR) MRI sequence has proven to be a highly accurate, sensitive, and time-efficient modality for detecting and grading chondromalacia patellae. Its incorporation of fat suppression significantly enhances its diagnostic capability compared to standard proton density sequences. Given advancements in MRI technology, coil design, and image processing software, PD-SPAIR should be considered the preferred imaging protocol for evaluating patellar cartilage abnormalities. This is particularly relevant in younger patients, where early diagnosis can guide timely interventions and improve outcomes. Therefore, it is recommended that PD-SPAIR replace conventional PD sequences as part of the routine knee MRI protocol, especially in patients with suspected chondromalacia patellae.

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